

ON THE BASICS OF MANAGEMENT IN THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM

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Abstract: Managing a medical organization requires a special approach due to the specificity of the product being released to the market—a medical service. The social significance of the medical business dictates the use of special management methods. While modern companies discuss collective management, quality management, and project management, most healthcare organizations in Uzbekistan continue to operate according to the Taylor model, adhering to strict subordination. It is necessary to emphasize the importance of high-quality training for medical personnel and highly qualified management staff, as their activities will determine the state of health protection and promotion in our country.

Keywords: Management, medical services, model, health protection and promotion, economics, manager, management personnel.

Introduction:

The President of the American Management Association once said that management is not about managing things but about influencing people. It is the art of achieving desired outcomes through managing people. Management (from the English "manage"—to manage) is the ability to achieve set goals by utilizing the labor, intelligence, and motivations of others. Management is a system of enterprise management aimed at satisfying societal needs through the production of goods and services in a market economy. In modern language, the term "management" is used more broadly than this definition: it is the science of management, a field of human

knowledge and theory that helps to perform this function; it is a function, a type of activity in guiding people, the art of getting work done, a process; it is a specific category of people, a social stratum of those who perform management work, a cohort of modern managers (the collective of managers); it is an organ or apparatus of management. The basic concepts and managerial categories of management in healthcare. The need to include this section in the textbook is dictated by the necessity of developing a common language for both managers and for formulating conceptual approaches to communication between leaders and specialists in the medical services industry at various levels of management. The foundation is based on concepts and categories from the definitions recommended by the World Health Organization for medical services statistics.

Defining management in healthcare. Can we unequivocally answer what is included in the concept of "management in healthcare"? For some, it is associated with medical procedures received in hospital wards, with medications, physiotherapy; for others, it is the hope for improved health; for others, it is treatment in foreign clinics. And they are all right, as management in healthcare (management of medical services) is extremely diverse. Effective resource utilization is impossible without competent leaders who can address current goals and tasks set in the industry. One of the trends in the development of modern society and social relations is the economization of various spheres of life, i.e., the penetration of economics into these areas. The connection between healthcare and economics, economic and financial processes, is becoming increasingly close. At the same time, the dependence of health protection on its provision with economic resources is increasing, and the influence of the health status of the population on economic outcomes achieved in countries, regions, and economic sectors is growing.

Research Objective:

To analyze the training of management personnel for the healthcare sector.

Research Tasks:

1. Examine the system of training management personnel for the healthcare sector. 2. Identify the features of training management personnel for the healthcare sector. 3. Provide recommendations for improving the training of management personnel for the healthcare sector.

Materials and Methods:

The author uses theoretical and empirical methods of scientific research. The work employs methods of synthesis, comparison, generalization, formalization, analysis of secondary sources, etc. Scientific publications, normative legal acts, free internet resources, printed publications, etc., were studied.

Research Results:

"Management is a specific type of activity that satisfies the objective needs of social production in determining the goals of its functioning and effective development, in developing the necessary means and methods to achieve them, as well as in coordinating the efforts of all participants in production to obtain results that correspond to the goals." The main goal of management is to ensure the effective use of resources: finances, technologies, people, time. To achieve this, managers take on specific tasks. For example:

- Organize the production of goods or the provision of services;
- Develop a system of personnel motivation;
- Analyze demand, target audience;
- Optimize business processes, production costs;
- Recruit personnel for a department or company;
- Develop a strategy for the development of a department or company;
- Assess necessary resources, find them;
- Control the quality of work;
- Develop regulations for employees;
- Automate processes, implement innovations.

Management can be applied to a project, such as developing a website for a company, a startup, or a corporation. Hence, there are different types of leadership. Let's examine the main ones. This concept includes project planning, team formation, task allocation, and result control. A project is the process of creating a new product or achieving a unique result. For example, developing a new website, organizing an event, or writing a research paper can be considered projects. Projects are managed by project managers. Their main task is to complete the project on time. At the same time, it is important to satisfy the interests of all parties: the company, the client, and the team. This is the management of operational processes and resources within a company to ensure efficient production of goods and services.

Operational managers control processes and continuously improve them. What is considered a process? For example, there is a website development process. It is established and repeated: you regularly develop websites for clients, know who is responsible for what, and how the work is structured. At the same time, the creation of each new website is a separate project, as the task is to implement everything from scratch, come up with a concept, design layouts, etc. Each head of a medical institution, especially chief physicians, needs to create new personnel management services, which usually arise on the basis of traditional services—HR departments, labor organization, wages, labor protection, and safety, etc. The tasks of the new services are to implement personnel policies and coordinate activities for managing labor resources in the institution. The basis of a medical organization's activity is the timely and high-quality provision of highly qualified medical care to the population. Quality management systems allow improving this quality and the degree of patient satisfaction.

Management, being a social institution, is particularly concerned with the productivity of resources. It is responsible for organizing economic development, which is why it reflects the main spirit of the modern era. Management is indeed

necessary, which is why it has developed so rapidly and practically without any opposition. Managing a medical organization requires two qualities: the ability to step back and look from a "height" and the ability to take responsibility for the results of subordinates. A leader takes responsibility not only for their own mistakes but also for the mistakes of their employees, and must act by organizing them, managing their working time, activities, and results. Only by focusing on "tomorrow" can one demonstrate their managerial abilities: anticipate upcoming changes, manage potential conflicts, stimulate employee activity, demonstrate leadership qualities, etc. In modern conditions, managing medical organizations involves transforming the functions of top management into managerial ones; leaders can no longer remain just doctors but must possess the full arsenal of management tools. By taking a leadership position, a person essentially ceases to be a doctor and becomes a healthcare manager—a hired professional manager, in whose activities economic and managerial knowledge should take the leading place. Skills in the competent management of human, financial, and material resources of a medical organization are necessary. The conducted analysis of the training of management personnel for the healthcare sector has shown the importance of obtaining special education in management. Professional training of management personnel in the healthcare sector involves mastering basic educational programs that define the types of activities, competencies, knowledge, skills, and organizational and methodological support of the educational process, which allows for the implementation of the training program in the field of "Management." Leaders implement their decisions in practice by applying the basic principles of motivation. Managing a medical organization requires two qualities: the ability to step back and look from a "height" and the ability to take responsibility for the results of subordinates. A leader takes responsibility not only for their own mistakes but also for the mistakes of their employees, and must act by organizing them, managing their working time, activities, and results. Only by focusing on

"tomorrow" can one demonstrate their managerial abilities: anticipate upcoming changes, manage potential conflicts, stimulate employee activity, demonstrate leadership qualities, etc. **Conclusions:** To lead is to ensure execution today while thinking about how to do things differently tomorrow. This means thinking differently to act differently, guided by the main principle in healthcare: first and foremost—meeting the needs of patients. Thus, the training of medical personnel should involve not only specialized state educational institutions of secondary and higher professional medical education but also specialized business schools. Since the training of management personnel for medical institutions is part of the restructuring of healthcare, such a systematic approach will provide the necessary level of not only professional but also business competencies required for modern medicine.

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